

Raising Resilience of Web Service Dependent Repository Systems

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Purpose Service Oriented Architecture has become a popular architecture in systems development, it is often implemented employing Web Services. However, the dependency especially on externally provided services can impact the reliability of a system. This is often caused by the looser coupling also implying a less stringent policy for change management and notifications. We therefore characterise the types of changes that can happen in remote services, and propose the concept of Resilient Web Services as an example on how to upgrade existing services to better support the long term stability of services and systems.

Design/methodology/approach Having analysed several use cases where systems broke due to external dependencies not correctly maintained, the authors derived requirements for Resilient Web Services.

Findings By means of a prototype implementation and evaluation of this solution in a case study, the feasibility of the approach was verified. Several scenarios of changes in web services were simulated and correctly identified, and responded to.

Originality/value The authors propose a set of extensions to existing standards such as WSDL to improve the long-term availability of services in Service Oriented Architectures. A prototype implementation was developed for service monitoring and Resilient Web Services.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Resilient Web Services, SOA, Monitoring, WSMF, Business Continuity, Digital Libraries, Repositories, Context Model

1. INTRODUCTION

Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) is a popular mean to implement complex systems, especially, but not limited to settings where some parts of the system are provided by external parties. Web Services are a popular pattern to realise SOA. While SOA allows for a rapid development cycle especially when existing services are recombined as mashups, there is also a threat of the reliability and long term availability of these services, and hence also for applications that build on top of them. These threats can result in an unavailability of the service due to a change in its interface, but also due to a change in functionality of the service, without interface change.

To alleviate these threats and uncertainties, the concept of Resilient Web Services has been proposed lately [Miksa et al. 2015, 2014]. Resilient Web Services (RWS) build on top of existing Web Service Standards, such as WSDL, by adding a set of methods available to the consumer that facilitate the management and use of the service over time, when changes occur. RWS build on a versioning of web services, and provide a messaging mechanism that informs the service consumers when a change has occurred including information on the nature of the change. The consumers can then verify whether their application is actually affected, and either opt to use an earlier version, or adapt their product.

In this paper, we apply the concept of RWS on a real-world scenario from the domain of digital libraries and document repositories. Trust in the long-term availability and reliability of the system is important for digital libraries, as external parties refer to the facts provided by the documents in the system. The system we study in detail is *Phaidra*, which is a system following SOA principles. It is deployed in several local instances among the various academic partners of the development consortium. Some of the service are, however, provided centrally by the lead partner, and are consumed by others. We demonstrate how these services can be converted into Resilient Web Services, mostly relying on infrastructure and information that is already present. Further, we investigate the required effort from the consumer point of view, and evaluate whether the usage of RWS improves the system's reliability.

The paper is organized as follows. Related work is discussed in Section 2. Monitoring of Web Services is discussed in Section 3, before the concept of Resilient Web Services is described in Section 4. Aspects and reference implementations of RWS are discussed in Section 5. Section 6 then introduces the use case of the digital library system, and describes in detail how RWS are provided and consumed in this setting. Finally, a discussion and future work are provided in Sections 7 and 8.

2. RELATED WORK

In this section we discuss what kinds of changes can happen in Web Services. Then we discuss how these changes can be monitored and detected, as well as models that can be used to persist and analyse these changes. We also discuss available extensions to Web Services that aim at mitigating the consequences of changes.

2.1. Changes in Web Services

In [Miksa et al. 2015] we divided the ICT changes into two categories: internal and external. Internal changes are all alterations that are under control of the process owner. The effects of any software or hardware modifications, for example installation of updates, can be traced, and the impact on the correctness of process execution can be evaluated. Furthermore, the point in time when internal changes are caused can often be planned in advance, and mitigation actions can be provisioned. External changes are modifications that are beyond direct control of the process owner. For example, when a service is hosted by a third party, it may happen that the administrator modifies the software or hardware environment, or the system automatically allocates different resources than usually. As a consequence, the customer's process is affected.

In addition to the internal/external distinction, changes can further be broken down into four categories that describe the nature of the Web Service change, as listed in Table I.

2.2. Monitoring

The goal of Business Activity Monitoring (BAM) is to provide real time information about the status and results of various tasks and processes, thus enabling the management to make better business decisions and quickly address detected problems and opportunities [McCoy 2002]. However, the scope of BAM tools is on monitoring and analysing the processes from a business view, and not on the underlying ICT infrastructure.

The framework presented in [Cao et al. 2010] generates and executes automatically tests for conformance testing of a composite of Web Services described in BPEL. This approach was combined with passive testing, which verifies time traces with respect to a set of constraints [Cao et al. 2011]. Both solutions are limited to Web Services that are implemented according to the BPEL specification. Verification of behavioural conformance of services during run-time is presented in [Dranidis et al. 2009]. Stream X-machines are applied to check the control flow of a Web Service and the generated responses. The traffic is intercepted from a live system and continuous monitoring for changes is performed. The Stream X-machine needs to be developed manually, and requires access to the Web Service implementation, which limits the application of this method. The authors also provide a classification of Web Services. Three major criteria are distinguished: conversational / non-conversational, private-state / shared-state, transient-state / persistent-state. In our work, we consider these criteria as sub-criteria of the stateful / stateless criterion.

The WS-TAXI framework[Bartolini et al. 2009] combines the coverage of Web Service operations with data-driven test generation. It is able to deliver a suite of test messages ready for execution, generated using a WSDL specification. WS-TAXI generates and uses purely synthetic data which may be quite different from the data exchanged in a process. It is thus more suited for Web Service development and testing, rather than monitoring of already deployed SOA solutions.

Table I. Summary of changes in Web Services [Miksa et al. 2015]

Change type	Description
Unavailability	Likely stops the execution of the process. The reasons can range from temporary technical problems, to bankruptcy of the service provider. It can be easily detected, for example by using time-outs which would alert to unavailability of the Web Service.
Interface change	Such situation may also be easily detected. It may require short pauses in the process execution until the changes will be adopted into the process. Of course, in case of significant changes in the communication interface (e.g. switch from REST to WSDL), time needed for reconnecting the Web Service into the process may require more effort.
Functionality change	Outputs of the Web Service change, while the interface stays the same. This threat is hard to detect, as the process may not break, but instead deliver outputs which are not correct. These could be, for example, changes at the semantic level, e.g. switching the unit of measurement from inches to centimetre due to a server configuration change. Other possibilities are bug fixes in the underlying algorithm (which may introduce other bugs as well), or intentional changes in the functionality, e.g. faster but less accurate computational algorithms.
Behavioural change	It may not always refrain the process from correct execution, but can occur temporally and therefore be hard to notice. The examples of such cases could be different timing characteristics or delays, effects of buffering, and so on.

Monitoring whether Service Level Agreements (SLA) conditions are fulfilled by Web Services is a problem related to monitoring Web Services for changes. In [Goel and Shyamasundar 2010] a run-time monitoring framework which allows accessing exchanged messages and comparison against designed scenarios is presented. The focus is on QoS aspects, for example of a time-out mechanism detecting unavailability of the service. In [Goel et al. 2011] emphasise is put on detection of violations at the functional level. SLAs are described formally using temporal logic and are used to verify the behaviour of Web Services at runtime, for example maximum response time.

The shortcoming with the above mentioned solutions lies in the fact that they demand specific knowledge on the kind and the nature of the Web Service. Also, the kind of change which will be monitored, is required to deploy the proper solution. In many scenarios, however, only the URL and interface of the service are known, but no information on whether the Web Service is conversational, stateful, deterministic, etc.

The Web Service Monitoring Framework (WSMF) presented in [Miksa et al. 2015] is thus designed to allow investigation of any kind of Web Service, and to facilitate reasoning about the nature of a service. If the Web Service is deterministic, the monitoring process can be launched and all four types of changes (see Table I) can be detected. Otherwise, the monitoring framework is not able to detect any functional changes, but the other three types of change can still be monitored. Details on the monitoring framework are described in Section 3.

2.3. Web Service Extensions

Apart from monitoring the technical level of services, several improvements to the specification of Web Services, which should lead to a higher sustainability of processes, as well as reduction of the need for continuous monitoring, have been proposed.

The Universal Description Discovery and Integration (UDDI) is a registry which holds information on registered Web Services. However, the registry does not contain sufficient additional information on the service that would allow the user to obtain information on the nature, behaviour, or quality of the service. Several proposals aim at enriching the purely functional description of Web Services (bindings, ports, etc.) with Quality of Service (QoS) aspects, for example timing aspects, availability, reputation [Comuzzi and Pernici 2009] and pricing [Liu et al. 2004]. [W3C Working Group 2003] specifies requirements for QoS for Web

Fig. 1. Overview on the Process Context Model: Core ontology and extensions

Services. It lists 13 points which should be fulfilled, but none of them concerns guaranteeing continuity or non-modifiability.

Another approach is to facilitate versioning of Web Services. Yet in this case, approaches do not aim at specifying a way to interweave versioning into Web Service specification, but present workarounds to deal with the currently underspecified Web Service standards [Kaminski et al. 2006]. One of the exceptions is [Kalali et al. 2003], which provides functional requirements for a registry which notifies clients when a version of an interface changes. [Kaminski et al. 2006] is a good example of the current common view on versioning: versioning is understood as a change of interface. Changes in functionality while the interface stays the same are not considered. In [Miksa et al. 2015] we thus introduced a concept of Resilient Web Services which aims at extending specification of Web Services, addressing the challenge of functional changes. They are discussed in detail in Section 4.

2.4. Analysis of Changes

For implementation of the on-site monitoring, described in Section 6.2, we use the Context Model, a model that allows for a structured storage and analysis of the descriptive metadata and documentation of the system [Mayer et al. 2015, 2014]. This model allows to store information of a complete business process, from the sequence of steps executed to the technical infrastructure (software and hardware) that supports it. It defines a set of concepts that can be used to describe the process. The concepts can easily be extended, if a specific use case requires so. The model architecture is depicted in Figure 1. The model allows for reasoning on the information, thus being able to identify which steps in a process depend on an external service, or which specific hardware and software is providing the functionality for another step. This allows for a detailed analysis of which parts of a system are affected by various changes.

3. WEB SERVICE MONITORING FRAMEWORK

The Web Service Monitoring Framework, introduced in [Miksa et al. 2015], can be employed to monitor services and subsequently detect changes. It consists of the following four steps:

- (1) *Capture* - the communication to and from the the service is intercepted and stored.
- (2) *Transform* - requests and responses are grouped and enriched with additional metadata.
- (3) *Reason* - data is analysed and a type of the Web Service is determined.

Fig. 2. Communication between parties involved using the WSMF framework in a proxy mode.

- (4) *Monitor* - requests collected in the Capture step are replayed and the responses obtained are compared against those captured in the first step.

The following situations can occur during the Monitor step. If no responses are received, this may mean that the Web Service is not available: a change in availability occurred, or a change in the interface caused the unavailability. If only some of the messages are missing, then we can assume that the service is available but only a part of the interface has changed. When the service is deterministic and responses do not match the ground truth, then it indicates a change in functionality. If the service is non-deterministic, changes in functionality cannot be detected easily. If timestamps of recorded messages are stored and time intervals between request and response are calculated, then a change in response timing behaviour can be detected regardless of determinism. The time period required to detect changes is mainly driven by the interval of checks defined in the monitoring schedule.

A crucial requirement for using the approach described above is that the Web Service it is applied to does not cause any changes on the world outside the system observed. In situations where this is not the case, e.g. credit card payment transaction systems, such replaying of messages for monitoring purposes cannot be employed. Thus, while not universally applicable, the approach is still useful for a majority of situations, specifically in e-Science settings, where Web Services are deployed primarily for information transformation, collection or computational services.

If the communication can not be directly intercepted at the service consumer or provider side, an alternative implementation is to use a proxy mode. In this case, the communication between the consumer and the provider is temporarily redirected through a proxy server, which captures the requests, and forwards them to the actual server; subsequently, the server responses are relayed to the consumer. Thus, the exchange of real requests and responses can be intercepted. Figure 2 depicts the communication paths between the involved parties in the proxy mode. Figure 3 shows the proof of concept tool that implements the Web Service Monitoring Framework. The figure depicts a situation in which three requests are tested against the originally recorded proxy results, and their response validity is evaluated. The implementation also includes the proxy mode.

Fig. 3. Software Support for the Web Service monitoring framework, including a proxy mode

4. RESILIENT WEB SERVICES

In this section we discuss Resilient Web Services as an extension to the WSDL Web Service specification. We describe methods that are required in order to transform a regular Web Service into a Resilient Web Service.

The main aim of the resilient methods is to help the WS consumer to react to changes within the service. The long-term sustainability and usage of WSs would positively impact the longevity of business processes depending on them.

In [Miksa et al. 2014] we defined principles of RWS design and elaborated a list of methods that constitute RWS. For the sake of paper's completeness we provide below the description of RWS methods and also examples of responses obtained from these methods.

minAvailabilityDate() This method has no input parameters and in its output provides the guaranteed minimum availability date of the WS. In other words it provides the deadline till which the given WS is going to perform in an unchanged way.

identifyYourself() This method has no input parameters. The output consists of multiple information:

- version - number indicating release version of the WS, the version number is updated every time the WS owner modifies intentionally the WS,
- description - textual description of the latest release of the WS, it should contain information on differences towards the previous version,
- methods and their types - a list of all methods offered by the WS and information on its type, there are four available types: StatelessDeterministic, StatelessNonDeterministic, StatefulDeterministic, StatefulNonDeterministic,
- first release data - date since when the WS is available,
- total number of changes - integer indicating how many changes to the web service have been detected since its beginning, it includes both expected (new versions) and unexpected changes,
- availability percentage - availability of the WS expressed in percentage.

getSystemEnv() This method has no input parameters. The output is an ontology describing software and hardware components which are crucial for functioning of the WS. To describe the system environment in a structured way, we employ a meta-model that is well-known and widely used in the domain of Digital Preservation, namely the PREMIS Data Dictionary [PREMIS Editorial Committee 2008]. PREMIS allows to describe various aspects of computing infrastructure, including hardware and software of systems, which is of particular interest for our purpose. The data dictionary defines five types of entities: Intellectual, Object, Event, Agent, and Rights. It then defines 45 concepts belonging to

these types, as well as relations between the concepts and properties of the concepts. For describing the system environment, we use the OWL ontology representation of PREMIS¹. Specifically, the concepts of *Hardware* can be described by name, type, and additional free-text descriptive information, while the concept of *Software* has in addition also a property to specify the software version. A piece of software might require another software to be installed to properly function, which can be described by using the relation *hasSoftwareDependency* between two specific software instances. With these concept, we can sufficiently describe the current hardware and software setup of a specific system. This detailed description is only available to certain actors, namely a web service owner who is providing the service on serviced infrastructure.

getChangesSince(DateTime) There is one input parameter to the method which is the exact date and time since which all potential changes are listed in the output. This date could be the date of the last request sent to the RWS by the WS consumer. If no changes were detected since that time, then the result is empty. Otherwise a list of all changes is returned. Each change is described with the following information:

- change date and time - exact date and time of the change,
- change type - type of change as defined in Table I,
- change description - textual description of the change, it is optional and to be used in cases when the change notification is done manually,
- change list - ontology listing hardware and software components that were modified.

Changes in the system environment can also be described using PREMIS. To this end, the *Event* concept can be utilised. For example, we can indicate a replacement of a software component as an event of type *migration*, with an associated description using the *EventOutcome* concepts. The old and new components are related to the event via source and outcome relations. Figure 5 provides an excerpt from an example response.

Figure 4 presents an excerpt of the XSD schema defining the format of the response send by this method. The types of changes are encoded as enumerations and the ontology with a list of changes is provided as a string directly in the body of the response.

getContact() This method has no input parameters. The output provides contact details using entities from the UDDI schema. The following information is returned:

- organisation - name of the organisation owning the WS,
- person name - name of the person to be contacted, it is not necessarily identical with the WS owner,
- message - optional message from the contact person,
- phone - optional phone number,
- email - email address used for contacting,
- address - optional address.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

Industry uptake of a new standard can be a slow process. Thus, we propose two approaches to make our proposed Resilient Web Services easier and quicker to be deployed. The first approach is by providing an external registry that monitors the service and its behaviour, and thus can provide some of the resilient methods without any need for modification of the original service. This will be described in detail in Section 5.1. The second approach is in providing tools to the service owner to quickly transform an existing service to a resilient service, by deploying it on top of a framework that already implements most resilient methods; we show this in Section 5.2 with a prototype implemented in Java.

¹<http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/premis.html#>

```

<xs:element name="response">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="1">
      <xs:element type="xs:dateTime" name="changeDate"/>
      <xs:element type="CHANGETYPE" name="changeType"/>
      <xs:element type="xs:string" name="changeDescription" use="optional" />
      <xs:element type="xs:string" name="changesList" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:simpleType name="CHANGETYPE">
  <xs:restriction base="xs:string">
    <xs:enumeration value="Unavailability" />
    <xs:enumeration value="InterfaceChange" />
    <xs:enumeration value="FunctionalityChange" />
    <xs:enumeration value="BehaviouralChange" />
    <xs:enumeration value="NoEffect" />
  </xs:restriction>
</xs:simpleType>

```

Fig. 4. Fragments of an XSD schema defining format of the response for *getChangesSince* method.

```

<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/premis.rdf#Event"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="[serviceLocation]/[identifier]/SoftwareReplacement"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/premis.rdf#linkingSourceObject"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="[serviceLocation]/[identifier]/SoftwareReplacement"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="[originalModelURI]#OracleJava1.6.u44"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/premis.rdf#linkingOutcomeObject"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="[serviceLocation]/[identifier]/SoftwareReplacement"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="[serviceLocation]/[modifiedModelURI]#OpenJDK1.7.u65"/>
  />
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>

```

Fig. 5. Description detailing the changes made to the system by replacing *Oracle Java* version 1.6 with 1.7

5.1. External Registry

To allow resilient methods to be provided on top of an existing service, without requiring any changes in the service or its deployment, we propose the concept of an external registry, which sends notifications to the service consumer. The main task of the registry is the decoration (design pattern) of existing Web Services with resilient methods. The registry is a service provided by a third party. Such an approach should substantially increase the acceptance of Resilient Web Services among service operators and thus considerably decrease the adoption time. In this section, we therefore discuss how such a registry works, what actions are required from the parties involved and in what way it can be implemented.

Figure 6 illustrates the process of converting a WS into a RWS using the registry. There are three actors involved: the Web Service provider, the Web Service consumer, and the registry operator. When using traditional Web Services, the WS provider publishes a WSDL specification of the WS, and the consumer uses it to establish a connection to the WS. In the approach utilising the registry, the communication is still realised directly between the

Fig. 6. Business process model, depicting the transformation of a Web Service into a Resilient Web Service.

provider and the consumer, but the consumer obtains information about the port bindings from a different WSDL definition that is provided by the registry operator. The WSDL that is obtained from the registry consists of two logical parts. The first one is generated using the original WSDL file of a given Web Service, by verbatim copying information about the Web Service methods. The second one provides bindings to the resilient methods provided by the registry. Thus no changes at the side of WS provider are required. Furthermore, the communication between the provider and consumer remains unaltered and therefore no unnecessary complexity is added.

The data provided by the resilient methods consists of two types of information: static and dynamic. The static information is provided once when a given WS is registered at the registry. This is only possible when the registration is made by the WS provider, because they have the necessary knowledge about the WS. An example of such a static information that can only be provided by the WS owner is the expiration date. The active information comes from the monitoring of the registered Web Service. This functionality is provided regardless of who registered the WS. Both provider and consumer can register the WS, however, it is recommended that the registration is made by the WS owner, because more resilient methods can be used.

The active information provided by resilient methods of the registry come from monitoring that can be implemented using the Web Service monitoring framework described in Section 3. However, the implementation described in [Miksa et al. 2015], which uses network packet capturing in order to collect data used for monitoring, cannot be applied in case of the registry. This is because the registry is provided by a third party and therefore does not have a direct access to the network interface of the service consumer. For this reason two alternative approaches can be used. Either a set of synthetically generated requests can be used, as described in [Bartolini et al. 2009], to query the original WS and collect responses, or the proxy mechanisms described in Section 3 can be applied.

We implemented the proposed registry in Java, and made a use of the aforementioned monitoring tool using the proxy mode.

We simulated changes on a number of Web Services for which we had access to the source code, to detect all types listed in Table I.

5.2. On-site Monitoring

In a second approach towards implementing Resilient Web services, we deploy certain components directly on site of the web service provider. Compared to the purely register based approach, this setup allows us to detect potential causes for service changes directly in the environment, for example, changes in the hardware or software setup that might influence the functionality of the Web Service. Thus, we can trigger in a more informed way when we have to run our monitoring again, and if changes occurred, the likely source can be specified.

Table II. Support of resilient methods in different deployment scenarios

Method	External registry	On-site Monitoring
identifyYourself()	Y	Y
getContact()	Y	Y
minAvailabilityDate()	Y	Y
getSystemEnv()	N	Y
getChangesSince()	~	Y
- change type	N	Y
- change description	N	Y
- environment changes list	N	Y

Most of the resilient methods introduced in Section 4 do not require an implementation specific to a given Web Service. As such, the hardware or software setup of the machine can be determined via methods that are generic regardless of the actual implementation of the Web Service, but can be determined in the same or similar fashion for all Web Services using e.g. the same type of Operating System. Some methods may depend on the specific programming language used for implementing a Web Service, e.g. the type of libraries that can be utilised, and the way they are declared as dependencies, but again, these aspects can be generalised for Web Services using the same type of development platform. Therefore, we can provide an implementation of many of the resilient methods tailored for a specific platform or programming language. These implementations can then be used by the service provider to augment the service to become a Resilient Web Service.

In [Miksa et al. 2014] we provided an example of such a Resilient API for the Java programming language using publicly available frameworks like platform-independent SIGAR framework², or utilities such as *lhw*³ for Linux. In Section 6.2 we demonstrate another way in which on-site monitoring can be implemented.

5.3. Client Side Implementation

Once the Web Service has been upgraded into a Resilient Web Service, the service consumer needs to implement support for resilient methods. This implementation can e.g. be similar to the exception handling mechanisms used in programming languages.

Due to the fact, that the Web Service communication is asymmetrical, i.e. the provider cannot provide any information without any prior request, the WS consumer must implement a method that regularly polls the resilient method *getChangesSince()* that provides information whether there was a change to the WS, and if so what kind of a change it was. Depending on the kind of change detected, a corresponding scenario can be performed, for example, the execution of the processes using this Web Service can be stopped, or the WS can be substituted with another. Additional information provided by other resilient methods may also be useful in selecting appropriate recovery solution. An overhead resulting from the necessity of these improvements should be acceptable by the WS consumers, because they are the main beneficiaries of the Resilient Web Services. An alternative implementation may use push-style notifications to propagate information on changes, for example e-mail. The advantage of such an implementation is the fact that no polling for changes is required. On the other hand, the client needs to support additional communication protocols (not only SOAP).

6. USE CASE SPECIFIC IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we describe application of RWS on-site monitoring on a Phaidra repository system. We chose this use case, because it is representative for other repository systems

²<http://www.hyperic.com/products/sigar>

³<http://ezix.org/project/wiki/HardwareLiSter>

that are also built following SOA. The domain of digital preservation, in which repositories operate, puts special attention to maintaining the high level of trust that the accessed objects are faithfully presented and therefore can be interpreted correctly.

In Section 6.1 we describe the architecture, role of Web Services and the organisational setting of the use case. In Section 6.2 we describe how we introduced the RWS and the WSMF into the existing system, while minimising the additional effort by reusing as much as possible already existing system components and models.

6.1. Phaidra Repository System

The repository system described here is a university-wide digital asset management system with long-term archiving functions. Students, researchers and co-operators with the proper authorisation can upload and link the objects which, among others, can be text, image, and audio files in multiple formats.

6.1.1. Architecture. The system consists of two main components, the backend and the frontend. The backend is realized with the use of Fedora Commons⁴, which is an open source system that allows for storing, managing, and accessing digital objects. The web frontend is responsible for the presentation of contents, or editing of metadata. The frontend was developed at the university. The frontend interacts with the Fedora repository through the Fedora API, as seen in the Figure 7. The backend may also interact with other systems to obtain the content stored on different servers (distributed content) or may use web services to get additional information about the contents or to perform data transformation (e.g., format conversion, video streaming). These services are of particular interest, because they may change in different ways and therefore alter the information and the content delivered to the end users of the repository system. For example, a scientific paper can be stored in the Fedora repository in three formats: HTML, PDF, TEX and all of them will be grouped under one digital object. No disseminators (services performing operations on content) will be used to transform the content, because the content will be provided at the moment of creation of the digital object. However, the same final (visible to the end user) result could be obtained with the use of disseminators. It would be possible to store, for example, only the TEX file and use web services to generate on demand a PDF or HTML version of the document. The second solution introduces dependency on the services (disseminators). Such dependencies are unavoidable in case of interactive contents like interactive art, games, computer programs, which need a special environment to render these artefacts, or when the original file format becomes obsolete and must be transformed into the one that user can work with.

One of the services in use is the image converter that is used every time users access a web page with a summary about a digital document. For example, if the user browses through a collection of PDFs and opens one of them then they are presented with a preview of the first page of the paper which is a PNG file generated from the first page of the original file. This is achieved with the use of ImageMagick⁵ and the corresponding Perl module which needs to be installed in the operating system underlying the repository system. If a different version of ImageMagick is used, it may happen that the conversion may result in a different output. Other examples of services are the video streaming service and the book viewer service.

6.1.2. Organizational context. Phaidra can be used by any institution on the condition that this institution joins the community of Phaidra users. The community is a forum to share experiences and work jointly on improving the system. Phaidra is a common product for all of the stakeholders, but each of them runs their own installation. Each of them may have

⁴<http://www.fedora-commons.org>

⁵<http://www.imagemagick.org>

Fig. 7. Backend (Fedora) as a mediator for services and content [Fedora Commons Community 2007] different requirements and therefore may develop different features (services) independently, but is always obliged to share these new functionalities with other members. Therefore, it is possible that some of the Web Services hosted at one of the instances of the system are used by one of the other partners. The consortium agreement does not specify any formal agreements considering SLA of shared services. In order to ensure, that any changes that may occur in the service hosted by other consortium member do not affect the given Phaidra installation, a mechanism that monitors the service is needed. Therefore, we proposed to use the RWS and WSMF.

6.2. RWS On-site monitoring

In this section we describe how we implemented the on-site monitoring for an existing web service, thus converting it into a RWS. We present actions not only taken on the side of the service provider but also describe in what way the service consumer can automatically process the information provided by the RWS methods. For this experiment we used two virtualized instances of Phaidra: one for the service provider and one for the service consumer. Thus we have two independent instances having one common service, which is image converter service.

6.2.1. Available auxiliary resources. We start by describing already existing resources that will be used during the implementation of RWS mechanisms, namely: an instance of the TIMBUS Context Model and unit tests.

The structure of Phaidra is represented using the Context Model. It provides a comprehensive view of the system, taking into account the high level business layer, which depicts the typical usage scenarios of the system, and also the infrastructure layer, which describes particular software and hardware needed to perform these steps. Thanks to such a binding, one can see which resources are needed to perform particular steps. For example, one can identify when the image converter service is used and what libraries and software are involved to operate the service. The business level components of the model were modelled once at the beginning when the model was created, the infrastructure level components are provided by software extractors that analyse the system and encapsulate the information about current configuration into dedicated ontologies that are later linked to the initially created model. The model is updated always when any change takes place and hence it corresponds to the current state of the system. Due to the fact, that the Context Model already existed, we decided to use it for implementation of RWS in order to minimise the effort.

For the reason that the major part of the system (frontend) was developed by one of the consortium members, we were also provided with unit tests that are used to verify the systems functionality and validate the correctness of returned results. The tests are

implemented using JUnit⁶, a Java framework for test automation, and using Selenium⁷, which is a framework for automation of interaction with the web browser, but also capable of validating web site contents, taking screenshots, and so on. The tests scenarios overlap to a great extent with the typical usage scenarios that were modelled in the Context Model business layer. Later in this section we describe how we use these tests on the consumer side of the RWS.

6.2.2. RWS deployment. We started the transformation of the image converter service into a RWS, by converting it from the REST web service into a WSDL web service. This required creation of the WSDL file and minor changes in the system setup, so that a different type of WS can be used. At this step we already included the RWS methods in the service WSDL file. All these changes were reflected in the Phaidra's Context Model.

In the next step we deployed the WSMF on the Phaidra server. The WSMF was configured to capture live traffic from the network interface and to collect the evidence for the analysed WS. Thus we created the ground truth data that is later needed for evaluation of impact of changes on the WS performance. The results of this assessment are used by the *getChangesSince* RWS method to provide information about changes. We used the Context Model of the system to provide information about its environment through the *getSystemEnv* method. Obviously, we did not expose all of the information from the Context Model, because this would be not only very insecure, but would also simply overload the consumers with details potentially not important to them. Instead we used Apache Jena⁸ and a set of pre-defined SPARQL⁹ queries that filter the information about core components of the system and their versions. Furthermore, only these resources that have impact on the functioning of the service are provided. Thus information relevant only for the given WS is provided. We use the fact that the Context Model ontology has mapping to the PREMIS ontology and therefore we can easily convert the results of queries into corresponding format.

On the consumer side we adapted the system to use the WSDL web services (by copying the related modified components from the provider instance) and added implementation making use of RWS methods of the provider. We introduced systematic polling for changes by calling *getChangesSince* method. When the returned result states that there was a change, but the performance of the RWS is unchanged, then no actions are triggered. This could be the case, when the system is modified, but the change of components has no impact on the RWS. In cases when, the change was detected, the method triggers execution of JUnit test cases that check whether this alteration has impact on the final experience of the user. For example, the change resulted in slower execution of the service, but the threshold defined in the unit tests has not been reached and therefore the alteration is acceptable. Finally, in case when there was a change detected and the unit tests fail, then a notification is sent to the consumer instance operator, including the change description and list of changes of the RWS.

6.2.3. Experiment. In order to test the proposed set up, we performed an experiment by updating all Debian packages of the operating system underlying the image converter RWS. Being logged in as root user we performed the *aptitude update* command and then *aptitude safe-upgrade*. As a result we updated 148 packages. We ran Debian packages extractor in order to identify these changes. There is no need to run other extractors, because the other parts of the system, for example, Phaidra's code itself were not modified. However, in settings when we cannot determine to what extent the environment can differ, all extractors

⁶JUnit: <http://junit.org>

⁷SeleniumHQ: <http://www.seleniumhq.org>

⁸Apache Jena: <https://jena.apache.org>

⁹SPARQL: <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

have to be run again. The output of the Debian packages extractor provides an ontology describing all installed packages (including their cross-dependencies) in the system.

In order to identify which packages that have been modified could have an effect on the RWS, we run a tool for comparison of ontologies. We compared the ontology describing installed packages before and after updating system. The tool produced two output files, first one with individuals added to the original ontology, and the second one with the individuals removed from the original ontology. For each individual representing a package that was added to the system we checked in the updated Context Model, whether the individual was a dependency to the RWS, if so, then it was added to the list of changes that would be provided through RWS methods if a change was detected. In the next step the WSMF execution was triggered and the requests collected in the ground truth data were re-sent and the obtained responses were compared with the ground truth data responses. The whole process starting from running the extractor, through making an ontology comparison and identifying packages that may affect the RWS was scripted and performed automatically.

During our experiment, we identified a *perlmagick8-6.7.7.10-5+deb7u2* package that could have impact on the image converter service, but the WSMF did not detect any changes. Therefore, the RWS methods classified this as a change with no effect. On the consumer side, the active polling detected the change, but triggered no actions, because the change is not affecting the performance of the system.

The experiment has shown that there are many ways in which the RWS can be implemented. We demonstrated that the reuse of already existing tests and system models can significantly ease and facilitate RWS implementation. In other systems and other applications, potentially different set of auxiliary resources is available that can be used to implement the RWS.

7. DISCUSSION

There are several different usage scenarios for the deployment of Resilient Web Services, with different actors and roles involved. On the one hand, there is a potential differentiation on who is registering a service at an external registry. In the ideal case, the service owner is performing this task, but there might also be cases where the service owner is not registering the service himself. In such a case, a service consumer might be allowed to register the service. Such a situation will also imply limited functionality of resilient methods – basically only the *getChangesSince* method is available, as all the meta-data that the service owner would be providing (availability, contact, and so on) is missing.

Another distinction might be if the Web Service provider is hosting the service using services from a third-party, e.g. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) or Platform as a Service (PaaS). In such a scenario, the IaaS or PaaS provider is the only one to provide certain information needed for the on-site monitoring and the *getSystemEnv* method, and thus the Web Service provider would become a consumer of this information from the hosting provider.

Web Services are sometimes used to create mashups combining functionality of various Web Services, thus providing a new service. If the Resilient Web Services are used to create such a mashup, then it is possible to forward information on changes from the RWSs used to create it to the mashup. Hence, the mashup is also a Resilient Web Service. In this scenario the mashup owner uses the *getChangesSince()* method to receive notifications on changes from the dependent RWSs. Such a *Resilient Web Service chaining* is possible regardless of the implementation of the RWS. The mashup owner needs to design mechanisms to handle notifications from dependent RWSs and add the resilient methods to the interface of his mashup. The mashup owner does not have to use the registry nor the on-site tools suite, as long as he does not provide any new in-house developed methods that do not depend on RWSs.

Another important aspect, especially in the *getSystemEnv* method, is security. Exposing the exact hardware and software setup to anyone on the Internet might introduce security risks, as potential attack vectors based on vulnerabilities in the hardware, operating system or other software components are easier to identify. Thus, in many scenarios, it might be useful to restrict the information provided by, or the access to the *getSystemEnv* method.

Other security-related concerns are also of importance. For example, encryption of the Web Service with one-time keys requires that the monitoring framework can still understand the messages exchanged. Also, tokens or authentication mechanisms that might prevent replaying of messages need to be considered. While these aspects can be easily circumvented with the consent of the parties involved, their commitment that this is desired and allowed needs to be explicit, and the monitoring framework by default is not configured to perform such man-in-the-middle approaches.

8. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we discussed issues of ensuring continuous and faithful execution of processes in environments that use distributed services to perform tasks. We focused on Web Services as one typical representative. We analysed potential changes stemming from Web Services that impact business continuity. Monitoring and testing of Web Services, as well as extension mechanisms enriching the Web Services with additional information on their behaviour and availability were investigated. Furthermore, a use-case implementation for a digital repository system was presented.

Our work put special attention to the recently proposed extension of Web Services, namely the Resilient Web Services. We provided a detailed specification of the resilient methods, and described two alternative implementations that should ease its uptake and make the deployment easier. The first approach using an external RWS registry allows converting any Web Service into a Resilient Web Service without modification at the service provider site. For that purpose we provided an enhanced implementation of the existing Web Service Monitoring Framework that uses proxy mode to intercept communication. The second approach is an on-site monitoring tools suite that enables full utilization of resilient methods including information automatically collected from the underlying system.

We tested this solution by applying it in a use case of a digital repository system, where that repository system uses Web Services to perform some of its tasks. We monitored the impact of the system libraries updates on the performance of the Web Service using the monitoring framework in order to identify any changes that may affect the consumers using the Resilient Web Service. By using the Context Model of the system, we were able to provide information on changes relevant to the specific consumers. Both of the solutions are capable of providing notification on changes to the WS consumer and thus contribute significantly to the minimization of the impact of changes in the ICT infrastructure on the business processes. Although the discussion in this paper focused on Web Services, the solutions proposed here can also be applied in other implementations of distributed computing environments.

Currently we are working on a catalogue of policies that express requirements for the WS owners who are willing to convert their services into RWS. Thus, we want to ensure that all of the independent implementations of Resilient Web Services conform to its definition and provide reliable information to its consumers.

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